

List of formal and grey sources

ID	Formal sources
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P31	Alwaisi, Z., Kumar, T., Harjula, E., & Soderi, S. (2024). Securing constrained IoT systems: A lightweight machine learning approach for anomaly detection and prevention. <i>Internet of Things</i> , 28.
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ID	Title	Grey sources List
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GL2 2	5 Smart City Vulnerabilities	<i>5 smart city vulnerabilities</i> . (n.d.). IT Chronicles. https://itchronicles.com/smart-city/5-smart-city-vulnerabilities/
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GL2 7	Customizing Cybersecurity For Critical Infrastructure: Finding The Perfect Fit For Smart Cities	Durand, J. (2023, December 5). Customizing cybersecurity for critical infrastructure: Finding the perfect fit for smart cities. Forbes Technology Council. https://www.forbes.com/councils/forbestechcouncil/2023/12/05/customizing-cybersecurity-for-critical-infrastructure-finding-the-perfect-fit-for-smart-cities/
GL2 8	How can we make smart cities even smarter? Start with Security Intelligence	How can we make smart cities even smarter? Start with Security Intelligence https://securityintelligence.com/how-can-we-make-smart-cities-even-smarter-start-with-security-intelligence/
GL2 9	Hacking Smart Cities: Are we	Paritosh. (2024, September 7). <i>Hacking smart cities: Are we prepared for cyberattacks on urban infrastructure?</i> Medium.

	prepared for cyberattacks on urban infrastructure?	https://medium.com/@paritoshblogs/hacking-smart-cities-are-we-prepared-for-cyberattacks-on-urban-infrastructure-472b33b2d30c
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